

CONQUERING LANGUAGE BARRIER: A TEACHERS' JOURNEY TO PROFESSIONAL ADJUSTMENTS IN THE TEACHING AND LEARNING PROCESS

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Conquering Language Barrier: A Teachers' Journey to Professional Adjustments in the Teaching and Learning Process

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Abstract

This phenomenological study aimed to explore the journey of non-IP teachers teaching IP students in selected IP schools of La Paz District II, La Paz, Agusan del Sur. The study investigated the experiences of non-IP teachers, their challenges, their coping mechanisms, and insights gained into the language barrier in the teaching and learning process. Utilizing the purposive sampling technique, the research informants were five non-IP teachers who were subjected to in-depth interviews. The findings revealed that the experiences encountered were the way they talk, their dialect, and the gap in communication. The challenges met were learning their language, dispensing knowledge, students' reading comprehension, and misunderstanding and misinterpretation. The difficulties encountered in handling IP students were the medium of communication, classroom management, school attendance, and understanding of the lesson. On the other hand, the study showed that the challenges and difficulties the informants encountered made them become passionate about teaching, motivated to teach students well, considerate in many things, and have a creative mind. The coping mechanisms included learning the IP native language, having students translate the language to their native language, and being flexible and adaptive. Further, their learning and realization included employing various strategies and approaches, a teacher must be approachable, utilize technology, be passionate about teaching, and there must be constant communication and interaction.

Keywords: *Indigenous people, IP education, non-IP teachers, phenomenological approach*

Introduction

In the teaching and learning process, the medium of instruction is one of the big factors to consider to provide real-world learning opportunities in the classroom. Shared language gives confidence to both teachers and learners to explore and discover beyond educational content. However, students, whose first language is neither Filipino nor English, often struggle to understand lessons, leading to a disconnect in the learning process. This issue is compounded by a cultural mismatch between the curriculum and the students' lived experiences and traditions (Williams, 2023). Consequently, non-IP teachers find engaging students and facilitating active class participation challenging. Addressing these language barriers is crucial for improving educational outcomes, and ensuring that teaching methods and materials are culturally relevant and comprehensible to the students.

Globally, the majority of cross-cultural adaptation experts consider difficulties in language acquisition as a common problem in assimilating into host culture situations. Such a phenomenon is typically linked to an inability to freely communicate with native and non-native foreign language speakers. In one study of foreign postgraduate students at the School of Education, Communication and Language Sciences at Newcastle University, UK, a mismatch of the language skills is viewed as the cause of obstacles in the educative learning process (Valieva et al., 2019).

In the Philippines, researchers identified a variety of factors that contribute to the undereducation of indigenous people. One of the concerns is the language barrier which is considered the major difficulty that IP learners encounter. According to Fiagoy (2000), as cited by Cabal (2017), the causes of failures include contextualizing; the lessons, and cultural values into classroom activities, connection between the school and the community, and learning support to Indigenous children. For non-indigenous language teachers, meeting the demands of indigenous students can be extremely challenging (Aporbo, 2022).

Non-IP teachers in Philippine IP schools face significant challenges due to language barriers, these includes, integration of the indigenous material (Angelino & Matronillo, 2020), unfamiliar with the cultural contexts and learning styles of their IP students (Aporbo, 2022), which can lead to lower academic performance and reduced participation among IP students (Napil & San Jose, 2020).

Locally in Agusan del Sur Province, some teachers were assigned to far-flung areas and trained to teach culturally diverse students, but still struggle due to teachers' limited grasp of cultures. Because IP students receive a subpar education, the challenge requires careful consideration among curriculum stakeholders. There were mismatched and incongruent instructional methods as well as pedagogical competency for non-IP teachers managing IP learners in La Paz District II. To date, limited studies and written works are available about IP education. Therefore, the researcher conducted this study to reveal the various experiences of non-IP teachers who are instructing IP students and to better understand how they were working in Indigenous communities to respond culturally to the challenges of the teaching profession in providing inclusive education.

Research Questions

This study aimed to find out the participants' challenges and experiences with the language barrier encountered during the teaching and learning process. Specifically, it sought to answer the following questions:

1. What are the experiences of teachers on the language barrier encountered during the teaching and learning process?
2. What are the challenges of the teachers on language barrier encounter during teaching and learning process?
3. What are the coping mechanisms of the teachers on the challenges and problems encountered by the language barrier in the teaching and learning process?
4. What are the insights gained by the teachers on the language barrier encountered during the teaching and learning process?

Methodology

Research Design

The study employed a qualitative research design to gather data, viewpoints, expertise, and firsthand experiences from educators. The "interpretive paradigm" of qualitative research stresses the experiences and meanings of the study participants. According to Tilley (2019), qualitative research explains how people make sense of their experiences and surroundings and the meaning they ascribe to them.

This study, which looked for the common essences of a social phenomenon among non-IP teachers at Langasian Elementary School, used a phenomenological technique and was qualitative (Jamali, 2018). In which, research participants' experiences are grouped, examined, and compared to uncover and interpret the inner essence of the participant's cognitive processing regarding some common experience (Worthington, 2013).

Participants

The research participants were five non-IP teachers with a minimum of five years of teaching experience from four selected IP schools of La Paz District II, La Paz, Agusan del Sur. The participants of this research were selected through a non-probability type of sampling, specifically purposive sampling. The researcher conducted an in-depth interview concerning the experiences, challenges, coping mechanisms, and insights gained in language barrier encounters during the teaching and learning process.

Procedure

As a researcher, I was aware that strict adherence to the research process was necessary in conducting the study. Through research ethics committee endorsement, the study will be accomplished by firm support of the ethical procedures. Therefore, the following steps were followed.

First, the researcher obtained authorization from the Schools Division Superintendent of Agusan del Sur before the conduct of the study. It was subsequently forwarded to the district supervisor after receiving the division office's approval and endorsement. When the District Supervisor approved the researcher to conduct the study, the letter of permission was sent to the school heads and a head teacher of schools of the research participants. Second, after obtaining permission, the finalization of the teacher based on the criteria given was followed. Each research participant was asked to sign a consent form informing the study's intent. Third, during the in-depth interview, research participants were asked to answer the open-ended questions intended to produce their experiences, challenges, coping mechanisms, and insights gained in the language barrier encountered in the teaching and learning process. Meanwhile, I conducted follow-up interviews, as needed, to gather additional data. The approximate time for each follow-up interview varied depending on the number of questions. An audio recorder was used to record the interview and a field note was used in the in-depth interview.

Data Analysis

I used content and thematic analysis to group the findings according to the major themes and concepts that emerged during the research and data collection. These themes and fundamental concepts were evaluated and analysed in light of the study's goals concerning the experiences, challenges, coping mechanisms, and insights gained in language barrier encounters of non-IP teachers during the teaching and learning process.

I cited each pertinent quotation regarding the coping mechanisms and teaching strategies used by IP teachers when instructing Manobo students. Each quote was given equal weight when determining its placement within the participants' expressions and textual descriptions. To provide a structural description of the phenomenon and identify the key features shared by all research participants, I divided the pertinent themes into units of meaning.

Ethical Considerations

The fact that qualitative study has sensitive data collection from the participants, the researcher, therefore, adheres to the ethical considerations of this study. Thus, the following considerations were observed carefully by the researcher in gathering the data.

Social Value. The researcher made sure that the design of the study, methodology, and data collection were able to generate relevant information that supports the objectives of the study. By social value, the researcher refer to socially collective beliefs and systems of beliefs that operate as guiding principles in life. This implies assessing the importance of the information in terms of the nature and magnitude of the expected improvement of an intervention (Johannes J. M. van Delden & Rieke van der Graaf, 2021). Additionally, it

was the researcher's moral responsibility to guarantee that all research was conducted in a way that respects, safeguards, and fairly treats study participants as well as the communities in which it is conducted. Study participants or host communities cannot be subjected to unfairness or cruelty on the basis of social or scientific value.

To address the issue of cultural sensitivity, the researcher ensured that the questions and their follow-ups were carefully crafted to respect the practices and beliefs of Indigenous Peoples (IP) while also considering the insights of non-IP teachers. This approach was particularly important when the viewpoints of the teachers contradicted those of the researcher.

The researcher maintained cultural sensitivity throughout the interview process which on the creation of environment where both IP and non-IP perspectives were valued and respected. This included being mindful of cultural distinctions and ensuring that the questions did not carelessly offend or misrepresent the beliefs and practices of the IP communities.

Informed Consent. As stated by Creswell (2013), informed consent enhances respect for others. According to this notion, study subjects ought to be regarded as autonomous people. As long as they are provided with enough information to do so, they are independent, self-reliant, and capable of making decisions for themselves. Non-IP teachers who participated in the study were urged to make their own decisions on their involvement.

To observe such, the participants were given a consent form indicating their willingness to participate in order to avoid violating ethical issues. The purpose of informed consent is to ensure that the non-IP teachers were aware of the possible risks, benefits, and alternatives to the research. This means that they voluntarily participate to the research study with uncoerced decision whether to participate. The participants also were made aware of their right to withdraw from the study at any time. Additionally, the appropriate procedures to be used, their statements surrounding confidentiality, and their signature are all affixed.

Risks, Benefits, and Safety. Since the study involved a native language of one's culture, I made sure that the culture is respected, which, if deeply analyzed, means appreciating its uniqueness, its diversity, and its intrinsic value. Moreover, respect for a language means respecting the beliefs and customs and valuing the important social function and the group identity and solidarity that it fosters.

According to the study by Creswell (2013), all research entails dangers as well as rewards, but the researcher must be sure to follow the principle of balance. People engaged may consent to the study's conduct and may give it their complete support as a result of the advantages or opportunities that may be advantageous for society, or more specifically, in the fields of indigenous education.

To attain this possible issue, the researcher works to ensure the safety of research subjects and maximize the potential advantages while minimizing the potential risks.

Privacy, Confidentiality, and Confidentiality of Information. The conduct of ethical research involving human subjects is fundamentally based on respect for confidentiality and privacy. Respect for a person's autonomy, a desire to help others (benevolence), and the trust principle are the sources of privacy and secrecy. Confidentiality, as opposed to privacy, refers to the right to preserve private information disclosed within a professional engagement with a researcher (Folkman, 2000).

The researcher's assurance of privacy and confidentiality extends to the profile of participants and as well as their responses during the interview. All the gathered data disclosed during the course of the study were safely kept through a locked file folder and must only be accessed by the researcher and any other authorized person. After the data analysis and aggregate findings, it is then disposed to avoid disclosure to the public.

Moreover, in response to this issue, the anonymity of the participants involved has been safeguarded. Coding was employed in in-depth interviews to protect the privacy of the answers and the anonymity of the research participants' personal information. Therefore, whatever data is gathered should not be disclosed with respect to the respondents' trust and privacy. (Bhatia et al., 2019) emphasized that the right to privacy, as well as the associated ethical obligation of confidentiality, allows respondents to restrict others' access to information about themselves.

Justice. Adams (2008) contends that all categories of people, regardless of their race, gender, ethnicity, age, or other characteristics, should be equally exposed to the risks and rewards of research and that individuals should only be included or excluded for reasons related to the questions or hypotheses being investigated.

In response to this notion, the researcher showed fairness among the research participants. They were guaranteed to prioritize their needs over the objectives of the study. The participants were chosen based on research needs and not with the expediency of the researcher. Additionally, the researcher ensured that there was no unfair treatment among the respondents. Also, the interview questions were free from biases. Moreover, through the provisions of the informed consent, care, compensations and reimbursement were observed. The researcher guaranteed that any benefits arising from the study would be made available to the research respondents.

Results and Discussion

Expanding the conversation about the study's findings was made possible by the organized themes and the developing within them. There were extensive conversations to determine how each subject aligned with the connected literature and studies.

Experiences on Language Barrier Encountered in Teaching IP Pupils. The emerging themes in this structured theme were the way they talk, their dialect, and the communication gap. The finding revealed that the way IP pupils talk gives teachers a culture shock. There were terms used by the teacher that led to difficulties in comprehending the conversations with their pupils. In addition, the Manobo tribe has variations of dialects. Research participants although had a background in their language, still felt alienation because of their differences. As a result, the teaching and learning processes were affected. Teachers were not effective in their craft since the lessons were not conveyed well due to the language barrier. Another concern was the gap in communication between the teacher and the learners. There were common words in Manobo and Visayan that have a different meaning. Thus, during the process of teaching and learning both teachers and pupils had a hard time comprehending one another.

Research in multilingual educational settings consistently highlights similar challenges and outcomes. The findings support the study of Cummins (2015) that students who are taught in a language different from their home language often experience difficulties in comprehension and engagement, leading to lower academic performance. Similarly, Wei and García (2014) found that linguistic mismatches between teachers and students contribute to feelings of alienation and hinder effective teaching. This is particularly evident in contexts where there are significant differences in the semantic meaning of common words, as seen in the Manobo and Visayan languages.

Additionally, research by Imanova (2017) on code-switching in classrooms reveals that such linguistic discrepancies can lead to frequent misunderstandings, further complicating the learning process. These studies collectively underscore the importance of developing educational practices that accommodate linguistic diversity, ensuring that communication barriers are minimized and all students can participate fully and effectively in their education.

According to Lee (2014), it can be terrifying to teach native students. Since they are unfamiliar with the pupils' cultural backgrounds, it is considered that teachers are constantly anxious and under pressure as they educate.

Experiences Affecting Motivation to Teach IP Pupils. The emerging themes in this structured theme were to teach them well, and eagerness to learn their language. This study revealed that the experiences of non-IP teachers with language barriers greatly affect their motivation to teach their pupils well. Some reasons that fueled them were the opportunists, precarious living conditions, and the remote location of the children. People living in the mountains were mistakenly considered illiterate by many due to the distance from schools, thus, most of the time discriminated by people and were taken advantage of. Non-readers who need help the most were another teacher's concern. Although considered challenging, teachers see to it that the knowledge they have is imparted to them no matter what. Exposure of IP pupils to unfamiliar details was another reason why research participants strive to educate them well despite barriers. They wanted to widen their pupil's minds in order to learn more.

Similar findings are established in the literature on education in remote and indigenous communities. The study by Daly and Sharma (2018) found that non-native teachers working in indigenous areas often face significant motivational challenges due to language barriers, which hinder effective teaching. These teachers, like those in the current study, are driven by a commitment to overcoming these barriers to ensure their students receive a quality education. Additionally, research by Madden (2015) highlighted that remote locations and precarious living conditions of indigenous populations often lead to misconceptions about their literacy levels, resulting in discrimination and exploitation. These communities, despite their geographical isolation, possess rich cultural and linguistic knowledge that is frequently undervalued by the mainstream educational system.

Moreover, the issue of non-readers in remote areas is a common concern. A study by Maluleke (2022) emphasized the challenges teachers face in addressing the needs of non-readers in multilingual and marginalized communities. These teachers often exhibit a strong dedication to their students, striving to impart knowledge despite significant obstacles. Furthermore, the exposure of indigenous pupils to unfamiliar educational content, as noted by Tanaka (2009) as cited by Sharma and Shannon-Baker (2023), often motivates teachers to expand their students' horizons, ensuring they gain broader learning experiences beyond their immediate environment. These studies collectively support the notion that non-IP teachers, despite facing substantial difficulties, are committed to educating their pupils and bridging the gap caused by linguistic and cultural differences.

Further, though experiences do not really affect the motivation for some research participants to teach IP pupils, however, the eagerness to learn their language is heightened. Learning their language means embracing their language and culture. Therefore, teachers learn to adapt to what the locals are accustomed to so that IP learners can relate to how lessons are being delivered. In this way also, teachers could integrate culture-based techniques and strategies in teaching that can create interactive learning which builds the confidence of pupils to participate in the discussions.

Research on culturally responsive teaching provides strong support for the adaptation strategies employed by teachers in indigenous communities. Taylor and Sobel (2011) as cited by Vass (2017) emphasize the importance of culturally responsive pedagogy, which involves teachers adapting their teaching methods to align with the cultural contexts of their students. By incorporating local customs and cultural practices into their lessons, teachers can make learning more relevant and engaging for indigenous pupils.

Additionally, Rahman (2013) as cited by Harrison and Skrebneva (2020) on indigenous education emphasizes the effectiveness of culturally grounded educational strategies. They found that when teachers incorporate indigenous languages, stories, and traditions into their teaching, students not only perform better academically but also develop a stronger sense of cultural pride and identity. These

findings align with the current study's observation that adapting to local customs and integrating culture-based strategies can create an interactive and inclusive learning environment, ultimately benefiting the educational experiences of indigenous pupils.

Challenges in Language Barriers Encountered in Teaching IP Pupils. The emerging themes in this structured theme are learning their language, dispensing knowledge, students' reading comprehension, and misunderstanding and misinterpretation. Research participants revealed that learning the Manobo language is one of their struggles because it needs cultural consideration. This means that the culture of the people should be adapted by teachers in order to adjust to their instructions. Teachers have to adapt to the locals so that the language and culture will be preserved. Teachers then must widen their understanding and must possess extra mile patience because it is not easy, it takes time and effort to learn. Failure to attend to what is needed to learn will result in an ineffective way of teaching.

A language is thought to be foreign if it is acquired primarily in the classroom and is not spoken in the society where the teaching takes place. By learning a different language, a person can interact with people from that language's native culture productively and originally, as well as in everyday settings. Gaining knowledge of another language opens doors to new perspectives, enhances awareness of connections between things, and encourages an interdisciplinary viewpoint while obtaining an awareness of other cultures (Moeller and Catalano, 2015).

Another challenge that emerged based on the responses of non-IP teachers is when dispensing knowledge. The way teachers interact with the pupils is crucial to the successful delivery of the curriculum. Therefore, when pupils fail to understand how teachers communicate with them, there will be no learning at all. As a result, teachers are unable to impart the knowledge.

Reading comprehension is one of the challenges of non-IP teachers in dealing with the language barrier in the teaching and learning process. Students' poor comprehension has been demonstrated as a result of the ethnolinguistic discrepancies between the instructional languages and the students' native tongues. Since the native language and the language of instruction differ in the classroom, IP pupils have difficulty understanding the ideas that their teachers are trying to convey. There is a saying that goes, you cannot give what you don't have. Teachers had a hard time making pupils understand because teachers, themselves do not understand the native language which is supposed to be used for communication to have localization (Oxtero, 2022).

In classes, teachers faced misunderstanding and misinterpretation due to the terms used by the pupils when communicating. There are native words that do not exist in the teacher's language and there are the same words but have different meanings. So, every time the pupils interact during discussion, teachers are keen on the terms used or else fall into misinterpretation (Summers, 2014).

Difficulties Encountered in Handling IP Students in the Classroom. The emerging themes in this structured theme were the medium of communication, classroom management, attendance in school, and understanding the lesson. One of the identified sub-themes was the medium of communication. Teachers had difficulties in reprimanding pupil's exhibited behavior in a classroom setting due to a lack of communication skills. This could be attributed to the theme, the classroom management in which teachers struggled to discipline their pupils because of the language barrier. They tended to be ignored due to the terms used which are unfamiliar to pupils.

Another concern of the teacher was the pupil's attendance in school. Due to learners' survival way of living, they had inconsistencies in attending classes. As a result, the lesson being learned would not be retained and would show poor comprehension. Because of the language barrier, pupils had a hard time understanding the lesson. This is another theme that emerged based on the responses of the research participants. This means that, because teachers cannot provide an interactive learning environment due to pupils' inability to communicate, the learners are incapable of comprehending the lesson.

Classroom management challenges due to language barriers are well-documented in educational research, particularly in multilingual and multicultural settings. Cartledge (2008) as cited by Becker and Deris (2019) highlights that teachers in linguistically diverse classrooms often struggle with discipline and behaviour management because students may not fully understand the language used for instructions and reprimands.

Additionally, a study by Van Tartwijk et al. (2009) as cited by Theelen et al. (2019) found that teachers in multicultural classrooms face significant difficulties in maintaining order and discipline due to communication barriers. They noted that when teachers are not fluent in their students' primary language, their attempts to manage behaviour are often ineffective, as students do not grasp the seriousness or intent behind the reprimands.

Challenges and Difficulties that Influenced Perception About the Teaching Profession. The emerging themes in this structured theme are being passionate, being motivated to teach students well, many considerations in teaching, and having a creative mind. The finding showed that the challenges and difficulties encountered in the teaching and learning process made the teacher passionate about his job. The teacher became more motivated to impart knowledge and wisdom due to the needs that underlie IP education. An education that is usually ignored due to geographical proximity, limited sources and support, and lack of respect causes a critical education gap. These are some of the many considerations in which the teacher sees that IP learners should given enough attention to have a quality education. In teaching, the creativity of the teacher also makes the children motivated to learn. It ignites struggling learners, lights up the brain, spurs emotional development, and most importantly it is an in-demand skill in the field of work. Therefore, teachers consider creativity a must to possess in the field of teaching.

According to research, students' enthusiasm and their motivation to learn are directly impacted by their professors' passion (Gilal, Channa, Gilal, Gilal, & Shah, 2019). Both face-to-face and online learning can yield these advantages, in addition to increased student and instructor persistence (Greenberger, 2016). Teachers who are enthusiastic about their work exhibit enthusiasm and emit a unique form of energy that kids are drawn to; it is an infectious type of positivity (Anders & Guzzetti, 2020).

Coping Mechanism Used to Address Challenges. The emerging themes in this structured theme were to learn their language, have students translate language to their native language, and be flexible and adaptive.

This emerging theme showed that the most effective way to overcome language barriers and challenges is to prioritize learning their language. It is because language is a potent instrument that can aid in removing barriers between individuals from various cultures. Everyone can relate to one another more deeply and comprehend one another's viewpoints better if learned. Using a second language to express respect and interest in another culture can be quite effective. It can also support establishing stronger bonds of trust with persons from various language origins. Making an effort to acquire a few essential words and pleasantries might help you make a good impression even if you don't speak their language well.

In addition, the translation made by the students who know little of the teachers' language helps teachers bridge the gap in communicating the learning objectives to the class. It helps the learning process be more interactive and engaging. As a result, the language barrier was overcome and the learners attained the learning goals.

The importance of prioritizing language learning to overcome barriers in multicultural educational settings is well-supported in existing literature. Ballantyne et al. (2008) as cited by Senjahari et al. (2021) assert that acquiring proficiency in the student's native language significantly enhances communication and understanding, thereby breaking down barriers between teachers and pupils from different cultural backgrounds.

Similarly, Darwin and Norton (2015) emphasize that when teachers invest in learning the languages of their students, they are better equipped to connect with them on a deeper level. This connection fosters a more supportive and effective learning environment where students feel valued and understood.

Addressing Difficulties in Handling IP Pupils in the Classroom. The emerging themes in this structured theme were learning their language, using varied techniques and approaches, providing activities to absent students, and using gestures for better understanding.

Another emerging theme was learning their language. This was the most dominant response of the informants. As mentioned above the importance of language in the teaching and learning process is, that language is an essential component of culture and identity in addition to being a means of communication. We can better comprehend and relate to people from other cultures by removing the obstacles posed by language. Another theme that emerges is the use of varied techniques and approaches in handling IP pupils in the classroom. Using this, teachers can cater to different learning styles and preferences of IP pupils. They also build a good rapport which is believed to be the starting point of solving any classroom problems.

According to Banks (2014), using methods that produce and increase constructive interactions will result in more successful classroom environments for both teachers and students. The absence of a learner in daily class activities is one of the struggles of non-IP teachers in conquering the language barrier. To make up for the learning gap with other IP learners, the participants revealed in this structured theme, that providing activities to IP students makes them achieve the learning competencies. Due to the absence of verbal communication caused by the language barrier, gestures were used for better understanding in communicating with one another. This was considered by teachers the easiest way to adapt and learn another language. It is because it could be applied right away or could mirror how learners react and interact.

Teaching Techniques Employed to Overcome Language Barrier. The emerging themes in this structured theme were employing ICT integration, bridging techniques, and pictures as visual aids. One of the identified sub-themes was employing ICT integration. As revealed in the responses of the participants, the use of technology motivated learners to be attentive in the discussion due to their interest and curiosity about the things they saw for the first time. IP learners were active in class discussions because technology made learning entertaining and fun.

Active learning, knowledge construction, cooperative learning, and guided discovery are some modern learning theories and pedagogies that are made easier to implement in a classroom by new technologies. With the aid of new technologies, concepts like teachers as facilitators and students as active learners can be put into practice. Technology tools give users access to more resources and have the power to relieve students and teachers of menial work so they can concentrate on activities that foster better cooperation, in-depth learning, and critical thinking abilities (Cennamo, Ross, & Ertmer, 2013).

Another theme that emerged from the participants' responses was the bridging technique. Due to the different types of learners and their upbringing, some learners understand the language used by the teacher. On the contrary, there are learners who find conversing with different languages, an obstacle to learning due to the absence of good communication. As revealed in the interview, the bridging technique helps every learner build a good rapport and develop confidence in participating in class discussions. Since people recall images better than words, seeing something visually enhances the likelihood that learners will remember it for the long term. Visuals aid memory retention. Students' motivation levels are also raised by visuals since they break up monotony and make learning enjoyable.

Teachers revealed from their responses that visual aids help learners maintain their focus and understand complex concepts through the use of pictures.

Techniques Employed Considered More Effective and Helpful to Learners. The emerging themes in this structured theme were providing visual aids, the bridging technique, and the Use of ICT. In the teaching and learning process of non-IP teachers with native learners, providing visual aids ranked number one as effective and more beneficial to learners due to its level of importance and convenience. It was then followed by the bridging technique, which provide interactive learning and collaboration among pupils that leads to building good relationships and the development of confidence in oneself. The use of ICT ranked number three because even possessing entertaining features that motivate learners in the lesson, it has a disadvantage which is the sudden power interruption. It cannot be controlled unless will uses a generator which is impossible in far-flung areas.

The use of visual aids in multilingual and multicultural classrooms is widely recognized as an effective teaching strategy. According to a study by Hibbing and Rankin-Erickson (2003) as cited by Leong et al. (2019), visual aids significantly enhance comprehension and retention among learners, especially when language barriers are present. Visual tools such as pictures, diagrams, and videos can transcend linguistic limitations and convey complex information in a more accessible and engaging manner.

Furthermore, research by Mayer (2017) supports the idea that multimedia learning, which integrates visual and auditory elements, is more effective than traditional methods. Mayer's cognitive theory of multimedia learning suggests that visual aids help in dual coding of information, making it easier for students to process and remember content.

Insights Gained from Experience as a Teacher on Language Barrier Encountered in the Teaching and Learning Process. The emerging themes in this structured theme were employing various strategies and approaches, teachers must be approachable, utilize technology, be passionate about teaching, and have constant communication and interaction.

Due to the experiences encountered by non-IP teachers on the language barrier, significant learning and realization were made. One of the themes that emerged is employing various strategies and approaches. Teachers perceived that when learners are given ample opportunities to be understood, their full potential will be shown. Through instructional strategies and approaches being used by teachers in a classroom, the learning objectives are attainable and classroom management will be easy. A good teacher has the ability to build good relationships with his learners through being an approachable teacher. When a learner is confident in how they communicate their problems and concerns to their teachers inside the classroom, they will eventually be motivated to perform their best.

Technology's role in education nowadays cannot be contested. Due to the demands of society, being technologically aware and skilled is necessary in preparing students for a field of work. Thus, teachers, aside from using technology in instruction to motivate learners, also expose them to the reality that introduces technology as part of daily life. Despite the geographical location, limited access to education, and language barrier, it is important that they are given the opportunity to at least experience first-hand.

In the field of teaching and learning process which involves a language barrier among IP learners, being passionate is necessary to possess by teachers. This quality helps them to be committed and motivated to teach despite the challenges and barriers encountered. A key factor in determining a teacher's dedication and involvement is their passion for teaching. According to research, students' enthusiasm and their determination to learn and accomplish are directly impacted by their professors' passion (Gilal, Channa, Gilal, Gilal, & Shah, 2019).

Communication is essential in the social activity of teaching since it has a formative effect on students. Both verbal and non-verbal components can be used by the teacher to help convey the material. Therefore, constant engagement of students with their teachers is necessary to develop confidence which leads to better learning and adaptation.

According to Thomas (2021) cited the work of the British Council (2020), the foundation of the communicative method is the notion that mastering a language requires the ability to convey meaningful messages. Real communication allows language learners to apply their innate language acquisition mechanisms, which enables them to pick up the language. The term "communicative method" describes a strategy for learning a language that places a strong emphasis on conversation as both a means and an end in itself. Through interactions with one another and the teacher, reading authentic texts, and use of the language both in and out of class, students in communication environments acquire and practice the target language

Suggestions to Better Address Problems Encountered. The emerging themes in this structured theme were adapting and learning their language and culture, and localization of curriculum.

The success of breaking language barriers starts with how you manage to handle pressure. Being able to be exposed to an unfamiliar place with a different culture as you have brought so much tension because you need to delve into how to interact with them without offending them. There are cultural norms and standards that must be followed to avoid misunderstanding and misconception that will possibly lead to commotion. Therefore, in order to avoid problems that may arise, learning their language and culture must in top priority to easily adapt what is used to by the locals. It is also a kind of respect for them when you show acceptance of their culture. Teachers, on the other hand, become more efficient and effective due to an accommodative sense of teaching that caters to the needs of native learners.

The process of localizing curriculum entails defining specific curriculum elements at the community, local, or school level, typically with the participation of local staff, stakeholders, and institutions, in order to address issues that are pertinent locally and promote richer educational opportunities. Based on the responses of the participants, it is suggested that when the curriculum is localized, both teachers and learners can perform better in showing their full potential and abilities. This is because teachers will be directed to the learning objectives and the techniques and approaches to be used for better outcomes instead of minding their competence about barriers, specifically with their language and culture. Learners as well, will not consume time for adjustments, but rather maximize the learning opportunity which has allocated and limited time.

When it comes to the globalization issue, localization is essential for the dissemination, adaptation, and development of a paradigm of knowledge, technology, behavioral norms, cultural values, and local values in a specific setting (Moradipour, 2017). Location-based curriculum design looks into how local resources and capacities are used to inspire and drive curriculum development. It also looks for ways to enhance meaningful learning experiences by incorporating local people, history, geography, and culture. The local curriculum's elements are arranged according to the cultural identities of the area, and activities are designed to achieve these objectives. As per Laeen, Ayati, Sani, and Booreng (2019, quoted by Haji Tabar Firouzajae & Mir Arab Razi, 2017), the local curriculum takes into account the development of students' skills, knowledge, abilities, and attitudes within a meaningful and relevant environment.

Conclusions

IP education in a classroom context has a lot of considerations to make by teachers given that cultural and language differences take place. Teachers must be equipped with qualities and various strategies and techniques in portraying the role of facilitator of learning. It is in response to the desire for inclusive education that necessitates assurances that aspiring teachers of indigenous pupils are sufficiently prepared to manage multicultural classes. Language teachers must be skilled and proficient in translating the lesson from English to the native language of the IP students in order to contextualize learning. It is important to prepare educational activities that allow students to express themselves freely. In this regard, the Department of Education may offer a range of seminars and trainings that could aid teachers in improving their lesson translation abilities.

Bridging the learning gap due to the language barrier requires teachers to embrace the diversity of the learners to unlock difficulties in adapting and allow them to create meaningful learning. Extra mile patience, creativity, passion, and compassion as well as the ability to respond to difficult situations must a teacher possess to successfully achieve and attain learning goals. Students must be guided and exposed to constant communication and interaction to learn and cope with the language barrier in the teaching and learning process.

Teachers, being the facilitators of learning that perpetuates knowledge and wisdom must be given ample opportunities by the Department of Education to provide various seminars and training about language pedagogy and multicultural education.

Non-IP teachers are encouraged to explore the instructional materials that are contextualized, localized, and indigenized to provide interactive learning which will generate in-depth and quality type of education.

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